

EXA4MIND

Building the platform for Extreme Data

DEVELOPING A SOLUTION FOR EXTREME DATA THAT
ENABLES ADVANCED DATA ANALYTICS ON SUPERCOMPUTERS
AND AUTOMATED DATA MANAGEMENT

APPLIED IN:

SCIENCE

INDUSTRY

SME AGRICULTURAL

SME HEALTH

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